

USING OF PAULOWNIA SERIES FOR GREENING IN THE ENVIRONS OF CITY

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Anatation

This annotation describes the bioecology of the pavlonia tree, methods of reproduction, the range and species acceptable for use in landscape design, and the advantages of using these species in urban landscaping.

Key words: trees, seeds, plant, leaves, air, landscape culture, region.

Paulownia – (Lat. Paulownia, Paulownia family) or. Adamova tree [1] – perennial, high (tall) (up to 15-20 meters in height) fast – growing, deciduous plant with very broad leaves (from 20 cm to 50 cm) and sweet – smelling blossom (till 30-50 cm length) of violet (sometimes white) flowers. Distributed in the North America, in Europe and Asia as valuable gardening – parking crop for the regions with warm and moist climates. And at last time, with searching alternative sources of energy it became very popular as raw material in bioenergetics.

Growing temps of the tree outstrip all existing wooden plants in the world and its wood becomes already fully maturity at the age of 8-9 ears old.

Leaves of Paulownia are unique according to their chemical structure. They contain albumin, protein till 20% per cents, according to taste characteristics they remind greens, lucerne, clover, that's why they are valuable fodder in animal breeding. They can be used for salads. They are able to absorb carbon dioxid to 10

times more than the leaves of usual trees.

Picture 1. period of blossoming.

Because of fast – growing of this tree it is used to create new forests. At present time demand for the wood of this tree increased in industry because cellulose is obtained from it. [2]

Its native land is China, where the plant is famous under the name of Blossoming tree of dragon and widely is used in public medicine, and in pharmaceuticals as well.[5] Extracts made of Paulownia leaves improve the work of the liver, the bladder, kidney, remove the problems in lungs. Seeds serve as the source of technical oil, and long ago they were used for the safe transportation of the expensive china goods (products).

In Japan representation of Paulownia (leaves and flowers) one can see on the coins and heraldics.

This plant (Paulownia) was honour for a long ago and has been being cultivated as Imperial tree. [3]

One more valuable quality of Paulownia thanks to its fast growth and active development of its root systems, planting this tree is able to prevent phenomena of erosion in the fertile soil areas, restores plots of forest which are suffered from fires, landslides and other natural destructions.

Picture 2. nut of the tree

Its big, downy leaves from both sides create splendid shadow and cool hot summer days. Thanks to that the leaves are very broad Paulownia cleans air successfully in more polluted areas and where the air polluted with poison gas as well, and its root system cleans soil from salts and heavy metals.

Its considerable biomass which falls into soil after fall of leaves enriches the ground with useful organic matters. [3]

Paulownia is widely used for greening of cities landscape, in gardening – parking for creating zones of recreation.

Picture 3. seeds of the tree

Incredible beautiful tree blossoms and its flowers fully open in spring, at the beginning of summer. Bunches are blue – lilac (sometimes light blue or white) flowers, consist of large (up to 6 cm in diameter) bell - flower flowers, outflow vanillin, with light, almond aroma that attract honey insects.[3]

Paulownia honey according to its components and flowers remind acacia and has a very valuable medicine quality. It is interesting that Paulownia flowers are applied in culinary as exotic little horn: in some European restaurants flowers are filled with dessert for giving aroma «tasty», dainty, unique to the meal.

Paulownia is valuable as aroma raw in perfumery and cosmetics (to prepare parfum, cream).

The main difficulty is the soil should be not very moisten and dry. The crop can be grown in the gardens, in the hot – houses, in the tubs and even in the pots (as indoor plants). [4]

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